

*** README FILE

*** Police Response Time and Injury Outcomes

*** by Greg DeAngelo, Marina Toger, and Sarit Weisburd

The code in this replication package constructs the analysis file from four main data sources (2009 DPD AVL Data, 2009 DPD 911 Call Data (sde_call2009.dta), 2009 DPD Arrest Data (sde_arre), 2009 DPD Crime Data (sde_crim.dta)) using PostgreSQL (together with QGIS) and Stata.

There are 8 files run in PostgreSQL to create the geographic mappings that capture the number of police officers in the vicinity of 911 calls.

After these steps are taken, one main master file in Stata calls all of the files necessary to generate the data for the 7 figures and 8 tables in the paper & one main master_appendix file in Stata creates the 5 figures and 9 tables in the online appendix. The replicator should expect the code to run for about 90 hours (or more dependent on their computer abilities).

1. Data access:

-**2009 DPD AVL Data** - provides information on the location and assignment of DPD emergency vehicles (The Police Foundation, 2009)

Variables: radio_name (car id), date_time, latitude, longitude, and master_incident_id (911 incident identifier if car is assigned to incident)

-**2009 DPD 911 Call Data** (sde_call2009.dta) - provides records of 911 calls (The Police Foundation, 2009)

Variables: id (call id), objectid (database id), servnum (call service number), call_dispo (call disposition – alarm, report, etc.), problem (type of incident), priority_n (priority ranking of call), response_d (date and time of call), time_fir_3 (date and time when first officer arrived at scene), address (address of call), beat (police beat), ra (police reporting area), x (latitude), y (longitude), location (location of call), caller_nam (name of person reporting call), sector (police sector), division (police division), district (police district), calltaking (name of person answering call)

-**2009 DPD Arrest Data** (sde_arre) - provides records of arrests (The Police Foundation, 2009).

Variables: servnum (arrest service number), arbkdate (arrest date), aratime (arrest time), arlbeat (police beat)

-**2009 DPD Crime Data** (sde_crim.dta) – provides records of reported crimes (The Police Foundation, 2009).

Variables: objectid (database id1), oid_ (database id2) servnum (crime service number), date1 (date of crime), beat (police beat), mo (crime description), ucr_offdes (category of offense), injuries, address, compname (name of complainant), compsex (complainant sex), comprace (complainant race), compage (complainant age), badge_id (responding officer), point_x (latitude), point_y (longitude)

-Dallas Police Department Reporting Area Measurements (ra_size.dta) (The Police Foundation, 2009)

Variables: ra, acres, population

-Dallas Police Department Beats shapefile (contains several files: beats_2009.cpg, beats_2009.prj, beats_2009.shp, beats_2009.dbf, beats_2009.qpj, beats_2009.shx) - (The Police Foundation, 2009)

Contains the spatial polygon shapes of police beats in Dallas, TX.

Variables: gid, beat, sector, division, shape_area, shape_len, area_ha

-A list of 2009 reporting areas mapped to beat, sector, and division (ra09_clean.dta) (The Police Foundation, 2009)

Variables: ra beat2009 sector2009 division09

- A list of the call problem types in the 911 data and their aggregation into broader categories (problem_categories.csv)

Variables: problem, category

The data used in the analysis was provided by the Police Foundation. The important steps for access are:

- a. Researchers can gain access to the data by submitting a written application to the police foundation.
- b. Data access is given to researchers affiliated with an officially approved research institution/university, based on application.
- c. The application should include a detailed research proposal describing the goals and methods of the project, a detailed list of variables, the selection criteria to be used, how the research will be funded, and how the anonymity of all subjects in the data will be preserved.
- d. The application should be submitted to Karen Amendola (kamendola@policefoundation.org)

2. Data access: **Dallas weather & sunrise/sunset data** (weather.dta)

This data includes daily weather characteristics for Dallas in 2009

Variables: date, hightemp, precipitation_cm, sunrise, sunset, date_date_ca (stata defined numeric date)

Sources: <https://sunrise-sunset.org/us/dallas-tx/2009/> (sunrise and sunset) and <https://www.iweather.net> (temperature and precipitation) (see sunrise-sunset(2009) and Iweather.net (2009)).

Data on sunrise and sunset in Dallas, TX were downloaded from the website sunrise-sunset.org. We downloaded each month separately. Data can be downloaded from <https://sunrise-sunset.org/us/dallas-tx/2009/1> , select the table and copy-paste to excel, keep only Date, Sunset and Sunrise columns.

Data on temperature and precipitation in Dallas, Texas were downloaded from <https://www.iweather.net/texas-dfw-weather-records>. We downloaded each month separately by selecting , Location: Dallas/Ft Worth, Product: Daily data for a full month, and Date: 2009:01-12. Select the table and copy-paste to excel, keep only date, temperature maximum, and precipitation.

A copy of these data is provided as part of this archive. These data are in the public domain.

3. Data access: **A list of 2009 Dallas reporting area characteristics** (income.dta)

This data was downloaded from census.gov and mapped to reporting areas.

Variables: ra hh_income per_capita_inc male_inc female_inc pct_poverty percent_black percent_white percent_asian percent_male percent_children percent_teens percent_20t34 percent_vacant_houses med_age ave_hh_sz

Source: <https://www.census.gov/data/developers/data-sets/acs-5year/2009.html> (U.S. Census Bureau American Community Survey (2009))

The data were all downloaded at the block level. We selected year=2009 and County=Dallas, Texas. Household income data were downloaded from table B19001, per-capita income were downloaded from B19301, the male income data were downloaded from B19325, the female income data were downloaded from B19325, the percent White were downloaded from B01001A, the percent Black were downloaded from B01001B, the percent Asian were downloaded from B01001D, population (total, percent children, percent teens, percent 20-34) were downloaded from B01001, percent poverty were downloaded from B06012, percent vacant houses were downloaded from B25002, median age was downloaded from B01002, average household size were downloaded from C08202.

A copy of this data is provided as part of this archive. The data are in the public domain.

4. Data access: **Annual Survey of State Government Finances**

Variables: state, year, expenditure_police_protection

Source: Kaplan (2020)

A copy of this data is provided as part of this archive. The data are in the public domain.

5. Data access: **Annual Survey of Public Employment and Payroll**

Variables: state, government, year, full_time_employees

Source: Kaplan (2021)

A copy of this data is provided as part of this archive. The data are in the public domain.

6. **Annual consumer price index across all relevant years** (cpi.csv)

Variables: year, cpi, index

Source: <https://www.minneapolisfed.org/about-us/monetary-policy/inflation-calculator/consumer-price-index-1913-> (Federal Reserve Bank of Minneapolis (2021))

A copy of this data is provided as part of this archive. The data are in the public domain.

7. Dallas Police Stations – dataset was downloaded from the City of Dallas open data portal <https://www.dallasopendata.com/Archive/Dallas-Police-Stations/si5f-a98p> (exported as a csv from the portal), the raw file is saved as “Dallas_Police_Stations.csv”. The csv file was opened in Excel and the coordinates were extracted (see the Excel file “Dallas_Police_Stations.xlsx”), and the result was saved as a csv with coordinates in “police_stations.csv” with unnecessary columns removed. This file was imported to QGIS and projected and from there imported to PostGIS as table named “policestations” (please see Appendix 2 below for more details as to how).

A copy of this data is provided as part of this archive. The data are in the public domain.

8. Programs – Most of the code is written in Stata the file master.do calls all the other files for creating the results in the paper. However, before this file can be run, we do some data cleaning in Stata and some geographic matching and distance measuring in PostgreSQL (including QGIS) as documented below.

Important: Within each of the codes runs (see steps (a)-(j) below) make sure you have set the correct location on your computer where the data is stored.

To install PostgreSQL please follow the installation procedures dependent on your OS (and later add the extension called PostGIS). We also used the extension btree_gist to make indexing faster, you can either add this extension, or alternatively run the code without gist (comment out all lines calling gist in sql). In the Appendix of this file (beginning on page 7) we documented the process of PostgreSQL installation on Mac Big Sur v.11.6.7. The file 0000_setup_mac.sql should be added to run before running any sql code (to start up psql in command line). To upload shapefiles to PostGIS database, install the latest version of QGIS (download the free installation files fitting to your OS). Within QGIS we used DB Manager to upload the shapefiles. For that to work, first install PostGIS, create the database you are going to be using, and add the extensions. Then you can add a new PostgreSQL connection from inside QGIS. After that, you can use DB Manager to upload the shapefiles.

The code for generating the micro data is summarized below:

- a. **data_clean.do** - this code inputs the 911 call data and outputs a clean file of matched calls to crime and additional files used later on in analysis.
- b. **c2c_export.do** - run in Stata to translate to Unicode, re-order columns and export data to a csv
- c. **fix_beats4calls.sql** in PostgreSQL - this adds missing beats using x,y locations (point in polygon spatial join). Before running this file, please upload the shapefile: "\\4 confidential data not for publication\raw\beats_2009.shp" to the SQL database – name the table “beats_2009” (see Appendix 1 below for some input on how to do that using QGIS with DBManager)
- d. **dist2pd_station.sql** in PostgreSQL - this adds distance to police station to each call. To run this first import the table policestations to PostGIS (see 7. Dallas Police Stations above for data source and Appendix 2 below for how-to).

e. **how2run_prep_avl_code.txt**, **how2run_prep_avl_code_indices.txt** (fix the paths to correct ones on your computer) These two files call code files and run them in PostgreSQL - that code imports police data from csv files to PostgreSQL and computes additional columns for further analysis. This took a long time (12 month-files, importing each file takes about half an hour, processing takes longer, the last file runs overnight, on my Macbook Pro it took a couple of days).

f. **ho2run_cc2v_sql.txt** (fix the paths to correct ones on your computer) This runs several code files in PostgreSQL - generate counts of availability by matching calls to police, add time when officer came within 200 meters

g. **ho2run_timeonshift_sql.txt** runs code in PostgreSQL that prepares police data only relevant for calls

h. **timeonshift.do** in Stata - Add beginning of shift, then time on shift of the assigned officers

i. **ho2run_count_officers_sql.txt** (fix the paths to correct ones on your computer) This runs several code files in PostgreSQL - Add count officers per day (ncars)

j. **master.do** in Stata calls all the other files for creating the results in the main paper.

k. **ho2run_add123wksago_sql.txt** (fix the paths to correct ones on your computer) This runs code in PostgreSQL - Add count officers at each location of incident in weeks leading up to the incident.

l. **master_appendix.do** in Stata calls all the other files for creating the results in the Appendix.

8. Software used

We ran this software on Windows server 2012 R2 Standard with 288 GB RAM and more than 4TB of storage space:

- PostgreSQL 9.6.5 with PostGIS version 3.2.1 and btree_gist (v 1.6) extensions
- Stata/SE 16.1
- QGIS 3.16.15 Hannover (used the DB Manager tool to import the shapefiles of beats, police stations, and divisions to PostgreSQL).

9. Stata packages installed

- matchit
- freqindex
- mtefe

References:

City of Dallas open data portal. 2013. "Dallas Police Stations."

<https://www.dallasopendata.com/Archive/Dallas-Police-Stations/si5f-a98p>

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The Police Foundation. 2009. "Dallas Police Department Patrol, Call, Crime, and Arrest Data."

Multiple files.

U.S. Census Bureau American Community Survey (2009) "*Income, Gender, Ethnicity/Race*". Tables B19001, B19301, B19325, B19325, B01001A, B01001B, B01001D, B01001, B06012, B25002, B01002, C08202. Retrieved from <https://www.census.gov/data/developers/data-sets/acs-5year/2009.html>

Appendix 1:

How to install PostgreSQL on Mac

This was performed on a MacBook Pro with the following specs:

First, download Postgres.app from here: <https://postgresapp.com/downloads.html>

Follow the installation steps as usual on a Mac – move the app icon to Applications.

Start the newly installed app.

Click Initialize – basically follow their installation instructions.

I normally use command line but if you want to use GUI – I suggest installing pgAdmin4 (works best).

Graphical Clients

Postgres.app includes `psql`, a versatile command line client for PostgreSQL. But it's not the only option; there are plenty of great graphical clients available for PostgreSQL. Two popular tools are:

Quick Links

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pgAdmin is a free software project released under the [PostgreSQL licence](#). The software is available in source and binary format from the [PostgreSQL mirror network](#). Because compiling from source requires technical knowledge, we recommend installing binary packages whenever possible.

The pages in this section give additional details about each binary package available as well as more direct download links. In addition, you can download source tarballs and pgAgent for your servers to enable additional functionality.

pgAdmin 4

pgAdmin 4 is a complete rewrite of pgAdmin, built using Python and Javascript/jQuery. A desktop runtime written in NW.js allows it to run standalone for individual users, or the web application code may be deployed directly on a web server for use by one or more users through their web browser. The software has the look and feels of a desktop application whatever the runtime environment is, and vastly improves on pgAdmin III with updated user interface elements, multi-user/web deployment options, dashboards, and a more modern design.

pgAgent

pgAgent is a job scheduler for PostgreSQL, which may be managed using pgAdmin. Direct to pgAdmin 4.0 pgAgent should be used

pgAdmin 4 (macOS)

Download

Maintainer: pgAdmin Development Team

A macOS App Bundle containing the pgAdmin 4 Desktop Runtime and

Notes

Install pgAdmin as you normally would an app – follow the on-screen instructions.

Start pgAdmin to check.

Click Reset Master Password and make a master password for pgAdmin.

In pgAdmin click on Servers → <your computer name> → Databases

It generates as default two databases: one called postgres, another called as your default username.

Create another database (I call mine dallastx). Don't use special characters, keep a short name, no capitals – its' better that way.

In the new database create extension postgis. If you want to have gist indexing add extension btree_gist (not necessary to get the final result, but if you run without it comment out all lines calling gist indexing).

Test the new installation – open terminal and start the psql connection. Check if PostGIS is installed and relevant SRIDs are there.

If all done right the answer should be 2.

```
dallastx=# select count(*) from spatial_ref_sys where srid in (32138,4326) limit 3;
count
-----
      2
(1 row)

Time: 0.500 ms
```

You can check which extensions are installed for a specific PostgreSQL database like this:

```
dallastx=# \dx
                                List of installed extensions
  Name    | Version | Schema  | Description
-----+-----+-----+-----
btree_gist | 1.6     | public  | support for indexing common datatypes in GiST
plpgsql   | 1.0     | pg_catalog | PL/pgSQL procedural language
postgis   | 3.2.1   | public  | PostGIS geometry and geography spatial types and functions
(3 rows)
```

Before running SQL code – open the code file, search and replace all data paths to the correct path for data location.

How to upload shapefiles to PostGIS using QGIS

Step 0 – install PostgreSQL, create all the needed extensions, create and populate the database

Step 1 – install QGIS (the latest stable version should be ok)

Step 2 – add a (new) database connection from QGIS to PostgreSQL (see below screenshot)

Step 3 – start DB Manager within QGIS and use it to upload the shapefiles into PostgreSQL tables

Importing the files, e.g. **beats_2009.shp**: in the folder "3 Replication package/input_files/" – there is "the shapefile" - a group of several files (see screenshot below, ALL are needed).

In the open QGIS with the created PostGIS connection as above, drag and drop beats_2009.shp to QGIS. If it asks about any coordinate transformation press cancel. In the bottom right corner it should say EPSG:32138.

Then open DB Manager and select your database, public scheme

and import the shapefile to PostGIS using the settings as below:

In the terminal window while running psql you can check that the import worked:

```
select count(*) from beats_2009;
count
-----
    234
(1 row)
```

The feature count should be the same as in QGIS:

Appendix 2 Importing Police Stations csv to QGIS

Open a new file in QGIS, select add comma separated file as below:

If the import done correctly, the stations should end up in the right places:

I could have imported csv directly to postgresql but I want to be sure that the projection is done correctly and see them on the map.

Then import the table to PostGIS as poliestations:

Appendix 3 Order of code running

Below is q schematic of how and in which order run the code.

